

Reactions of Sodium Cobaltinitrite with Bidentate Ligands— Synthesis of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cobalt(III)

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The reaction of sodium cobaltinitrite, $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ with dibasic tetradentate Schiff base (S.B.) is known to produce $\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{S.B.})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ ¹. The reactions of bidentate ligands with $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ however may lead to the total and/or partial replacement of the nitro groups resulting in the formation of either simple cobalt(III) complexes of the corresponding bidentate ligands or mixed-ligand complexes involving both the bidentate ligands and the nitrogroups. With a view to investigate the nature of such reactions, $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ was brought into reactions with some monobasic and as well as neutral bidentate ligands including Schiff bases.

Results and Discussion

With non-basic bidentate ligands, complexes 1–3 (Table 1) were obtained as residue. The complex 1 was however isolated as a by-product from a different reaction². The monoquo-complexes (4–6) were obtained from the filtrate. With basic-bidentate ligands, complexes 4–7 were separated from the filtrates as fine powder. The

corresponding monoquo-complexes (11–14) were isolated as the residues.

The three electronic spectral bands (Table 2) observed at 30 000–15 000 cm^{-1} are typical for pseudo-octahedral complexes of cobalt(III)³. The first band at 27 000–25 000 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition mixed up with metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition. The other two bands may be assigned due to the split components of ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition.

The infrared spectra of various Schiff bases and their metallic complexes have been investigated thoroughly^{4,5} and the results of these investigations are found to be valid in the present complexes. The presence of coordinated C=N groups in the present complexes is indicated by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands⁶ at 1 590–1 640 cm^{-1} . The acetylacetonate complex shows at $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ at 1 500–1 570 cm^{-1} while $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ is observed at 1 520–1 540 cm^{-1} , which suggest⁷ the presence of oxygen bonded acetylacetonate anion. $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ for the carbon bonded acetylacetonate⁸ appears above 1 650 cm^{-1} . The

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd./ (Colour)*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Co
2	Na[Co(BZEN)(NO ₂) ₄]b (Brown)	38.10 (38.24)	3.04 3.19	16.07 16.73	11.90 11.76
3	Na[Co(BZEN)(NO ₂) ₄]b (Brown)	40.02 (39.53)	3.61 3.48	15.79 16.27	11.11 11.43
4	[Co(En)(NO ₂) ₃ (H ₂ O)] (Orange yellow)	9.18 (8.72)	3.81 3.64	23.98 25.45	22.34 21.45
5	[Co(BZEN)(NO ₂) ₃ (H ₂ O)] (Brownish green)	43.34 (42.57)	4.10 3.99	15.09 15.52	12.88 13.08
7	Na[Co(acac) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂] (Dark red)	32.24 (32.08)	4.42 4.28	7.08 7.49	14.95 15.77
8	Na[Co(sal) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂] (Dark yellow)	38.96 (40.00)	2.51 2.38	6.23 6.67	13.66 14.05
9	Na[Co(SALENOL) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂] (Dark brown)	44.58 (45.09)	4.20 4.18	12.04 11.69	12.87 12.32
10	Na[Co(SALOP) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂] (Black)	53.02 (53.52)	3.77 3.60	9.09 9.60	10.34 10.12
11	[Co(acac) ₂ (NO ₂)(H ₂ O)] (Brownish green)	19.11 (18.69)	3.01 3.12	4.07 4.36	18.69 18.38
14	[Co(SALOP) ₂ (NO ₂)(H ₂ O)] (Greenish brown)	55.94 (56.83)	4.62 4.37	7.41 7.65	11.12 10.75

*M.p. of 2-8 and 11, ~ 250°d, of 9, 10 and 14, >300°d; Λ (Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹); 7, 108; 8, 98; 9, 118; 10, 94.

bands at 1 300–1 350 cm⁻¹ may be assigned due to coordinated phenolic C=O. Because of some controversy^{4,9}, and also due to the fact that at ~ 1 550–1 610 cm⁻¹ ν_{C-O} , δ_{OH_2} and δ_{NH_2} interfere¹⁰, these assignments are to be considered as tentative. The bands at ~ 1 350 and ~ 1 320 cm⁻¹ and a medium but sharp band near 830 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to NO₂ asymmetric stretch, NO₂ symmetric stretch and NO₂ bending vibrations¹⁰. The appearance of both NO₂ stretch and NO₂-bend bands supports the presence of

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹) (log ϵ)	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
2	26 410, 23 900, 19 650, 16 124	3 530, 3 300–3 240, 1 595, 1 415, 1 365, 1 330, 1 290, 1 250, 1 177, 1 135, 1 105, 1 055, 1 030, 970, 840, 825, 765, 720
7	39 215 (4.72), 26 322 (3.71), 20 852, 16 639	3 380, 2 710, 1 570, 1 550, 1 520, 1 515, 1 360, 1 325, 960, 880, 820, 770, 714
8	—	3 420–3 360, 1 650, 1 600, 1 500, 1 460, 1 405, 1 320, 1 170, 1 150, 1 120, 895, 850, 745, 725, 655
9	40 000 (4.60), 26 314 (3.74), 21 015, 17 075 (2.48)	3 570–3 470, 1 635, 1 600, 1 530, 1 510, 1 370, 1 315, 1 260, 1 195, 1 145, 1 120, 1 060, 1 050, 1 030, 955, 930, 890, 835, 760, 650
10	40 225 (4.64), 26 666 (3.80), 21 000, 16 510	3 420–3 380, 1 605, 1 525, 1 510, 1 500, 1 410, 1 350, 1 320, 1 190, 1 170, 1 150, 895, 845, 725, 655
11	25 310, 23 366, 21 715, 19 850, 16 100	—
14	26 100, 22 105, 20 880, 18 225, 15 800	—

N-bonded NO₂ group. Now the presence of both N-bonded NO₂ group and O-bonded phenolic oxygen makes interpretation of the ir spectral data in the region 1 300–1 400 cm⁻¹ very difficult.

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of benzaldehyde with ethylenediamine (BZEN) and 1,3-diaminopropane (BZPN) and also from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with ethanolamine (SALENOL) and *o*-aminophenol (SALOP) in ethanol medium. The liquids (BZEN and BZPN) were purified by fractional distillation under reduced pressure and the solids (SALOP and SALENOL) by recrystallisation from ethanol. Acetylacetone, ethylenediamine and salicylaldehyde (all A.R.) were used as purchased. Sodium cobaltinitrite was prepared by the literature method¹¹. Elemental analyses were done by conventional methods. Microanalyses of C and H were done at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U-3400 spectrophotometer and the infrared spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer. Conductivity was measured by using a Mullard conductivity bridge in MeOH (10⁻³ M solution).

Preparation of complexes: A mixture of ethanolic solutions of the bidentate ligands and Na₂[Co(NO₂)₆] dissolved in minimum volume of aqueous ethanol (1 : 2, v/v) in equimolar quantities, was heated on a water-bath for 20 min, then cooled to room temperature and filtered. The residue yielded complexes Na[Co(En)(NO₂)₄] (1), Na[Co(BZEN)(NO₂)₄] (2) and Na[Co(BZPN)(NO₂)₄] (3), which were washed with alcohol and ether. The monoquo-complexes [Co(En)(NO₂)₃(H₂O)] (4), [Co(BZEN)(NO₂)₃(H₂O)] (5) and [Co(BZPN)(NO₂)₃(H₂O)] (6) were obtained in small amounts on cooling the filtrate to 0° and then washed with pre-cooled alcohol and ether. On the other hand, complexes Na[Co(acac)₂(NO₂)₂] (7), Na[Co(sal)₂(NO₂)₂] (8), Na[Co(SALENOL)₂(NO₂)₂] (9) and Na[Co(SALOP)₂(NO₂)₂] (10) were obtained on cooling the filtrate to 0° after reduction of the volume and were washed with pre-cooled alcohol and ether. The corresponding monoquo-complexes [Co(acac)₂(NO₂)(H₂O)] (11), [Co(sal)₂(NO₂)(H₂O)] (12), [Co(SALENOL)(NO₂)(H₂O)] (13) and [Co(SALOP)(NO₂)(H₂O)] (14) were obtained as residues in small quantities. All the complexes were dried over fused CaCl₂.

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References

1. K. DEY and R. L. DE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 843.
2. R. L. DE, S. K. BHAR and S. KANUNGC, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, 69, 0C0.

3. R. A. D. WENWORTH and T. S. PIPER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 202; J. T. LEGG and D. W. COOKE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1576; 1965, 5, 595; K. KURODA and P. S. GENTILE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 155; J. H. DUNLOP and R. D. GILLARD, *Mol. Phys.*, 1963-64, 7, 493.
4. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1805.
5. B. D. SHARMA and J. C. BAILOR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5476; K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 998; 1956, 60, 1270.
6. J. E. KOVACIC, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 1967, 23, 183.
7. L. J. BOUCHER and D. R. HERINGTON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 4349.
8. J. LEWIS, R. F. LONG and C. OLDHAM, *J. Chem Soc. (A)*, 1965, 6740.
9. A. BIGOTTO, V. GALSANO and G. DEALTI, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1972, 28, 1581.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
11. "Handbook of preparative Inorganic Chemistry", ed. G. BAUER, Academic, New York, 1965, Vol. 2, 1531.